

Excess Volumes of Ternary Mixtures containing n-Butyl acetate, Aromatic Hydrocarbons and n-Butanol at 303.15 K

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Excess volumes (V_{ijk}^E) of n-butyl acetate (i) + benzene (j) + n-butanol (k), n-butyl acetate (i) + toluene (j) + n-butanol (k), n-butyl acetate (i) + chlorobenzene (j) + n-butanol (k), n-butyl acetate (i) + bromobenzene (j) + n-butanol (k), n-butyl acetate (i) + nitrobenzene (j) + n-butanol (k) mixtures have been measured dilatometrically at 303.15 K. The data have been examined in terms of the Redlich-Kister, Kohler and Tsao-Smith equations to predict these excess properties from the binary mixtures. The empirical correlating of Tsao-Smith and Redlich-Kister is the best for these systems.

Mixing volume effects are important from both theoretical and practical point of view. Indeed, strong deviations from linearity are often encountered in liquid mixtures, even of similar nature. In addition to the scientific interest, the knowledge of the mentioned phenomena is very useful for a number of practical applications in various fields; suffice it to mention here the field of paints, varnishes and printing inks where volume effects are involved in the conversion of formulations from a gravimetric into a volumetric base.

In a binary $i + j$ mixture, $i-i$ and $i-j$ contacts in the pure components i and j are replaced by $i-j$ contacts in the mixture. If interactions in a ternary $i + j + k$ mixture are assumed to be closely dependent on the interactions in the constituent $i + j$, $j + k$ and $i + k$ mixtures, it should be possible to evaluate the thermodynamic excess functions for the ternary mixtures of non-electrolytes when the corresponding functions for the binary $i + j$, $j + k$ and $i + k$ mixtures are known.

Theoretical predictions of excess molar volume of non-ideal binary liquid mixtures have been satisfactory in explaining the sign and magnitude in terms of the extent of interactions between mixing components¹. For ternary mixtures, the predictive approach is more complex and thus empirical methods based on experimental binary data have to be used². However, if significant interactions among the liquids occur, considerable errors may be introduced if we attempt to express the excess molar volume of ternary systems in terms of binary contributions. A search of the literature on ternary mixtures suggested the avail-

ability of several empirical relations used to calculate the excess volumes^{3,4} and did not reveal any data on this titled systems. Hence we report here the excess volumes of five ternary mixtures comprising of n-butylacetate, n-butanol and benzene, toluene, chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene respectively, and the experimental results were also used to check the capability of the predictive relations². We undertook this study on ternary mixtures of the titled systems with the object of determining the structure-breaking effects of the components.

Results and Discussion

The measured density and boiling point data along with the literature values⁴ are presented in Table 1. The V_{ijk}^E data for the various ternary ($i + j + k$) mixtures as a functions of composition at 303.15 K are recorded in Table 2. The binary excess volume data for n-butyl acetate with the aromatic hydrocarbons and n-butyl acetate with n-butanol and n-butanol with the aromatic hydrocarbons were taken from literature⁶. The ternary excess volume data, predicted by using the binary data through the empirical equations proposed by Redlich and Kister, Kohler and Tsao and Smith, are given in Table 2. The three empirical equations are as follows.

The Redlich-Kister expression :

$$V_{ij}^E = X_1 X_j [A_{ij} + B_{ij} (X_1 - X_j) + C_{ij} (X_1 - X_j)^2] \quad (1)$$

where, X_1 and X_j are the mole fractions of the components in a ternary mixture. The binary parameters are given in Table 3.

TABLE 1—BOILING POINT AND DENSITY DATA OF PURE COMPONENTS AT 303.15 K

Compd.	B.p. (K) :		ρ (g cm ⁻³) :
	Expt./ (Lit. ⁵)	Expt./ (Lit. ⁵)	
n-Butyl acetate	399.1 (399.3)	0.871 31 (0.871 29)	
n-Butanol	3.90.7 (390.8)	0.802 01 (0.802 06)	
Benzene	353.0 (353.2)	0.873 63 (0.873 63)	
Toluene	383.6 (383.8)	0.862 26 (0.862 32)	
Chlorobenzene	404.6 (404.8)	1.095 52 (1.095 50)	
Bromobenzene	428.3 (428.5)	1.481 48 (1.481 50)	
Nitrobenzene	483.8 (483.9)	1.193 46 (1.193 41)	

The Kohler expression :

$$V_{123}^E = (X_1 + X_2)^2 V_{12}^E + (X_1 + X_3)^2 V_{13}^E + (X_2 + X_3)^2 V_{23}^E \quad (2)$$

where, $V_{ij}^E = X_i' X_j' \sum_{s=0}^n (A_s)_{ij} (X_i' - X_j')^s$

at composition (X_i', X_j') , such that

$$X_i' = 1 - X_j' = X_i / (X_i + X_j)$$

where, X_i and X_j are the mole fractions of components i and j in a ternary mixture and $(A_s)_{ij}$'s are the parameters in the Kohler equation.

The Tsao-Smith expression :

$$V_{123}^E = X_2 (1 - X_1)^{-1} V_{12}^E + X_3 (1 - X_1)^{-1} V_{13}^E + (1 - X_1) V_{23}^E \quad (3)$$

where, V_{12}^E , V_{13}^E and V_{23}^E are the binary excess volumes at composition (X_i', X_j') such that $X_i' = X_i$ for 1, 2 and 1, 3 binary systems and $X_2' = X_2 / (X_2 + X_3)$ for 2, 3 binary systems.

The dependence of experimental ternary excess volumes V_{123}^E (exp) on composition is expressed by the modified Redlich-Kister expression,

$$V_{123}^E \text{ (exp)} = V_{123}^E \text{ (b)} + X_1 X_2 X_3 [A + B X_1 (X_2 - X_3) + C X_1^2 (X_2 - X_3)^2] \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } V_{123}^E \text{ (b)} = V_{12}^E + V_{23}^E + V_{13}^E \quad (5)$$

where, X_1 , X_2 and X_3 are the ternary mole fractions of n-butyl acetate, aromatic hydrocarbon and n-butanol and V_{123}^E (b) is the ternary excess volume computed from the binary data through the Redlich-Kister relation. The difference between V_{123}^E (exp) and V_{123}^E (b) is designated as deviation and is denoted by ΔV_{123}^E exp. ΔV_{123}^E is the deviation from V_{123}^E (expt) values. A , B and C are the ternary constants and are given in Table 4 along with the standard deviation $\sigma(\Delta V^E)$. The standard deviation $\sigma(\Delta V_{123}^E)$ was calculated using the relation,

$$\sigma(\Delta V_{123}^E) = \left[\frac{\sum \{ \Delta V_{123}^E(\text{expt}) - \Delta V_{123}^E(\text{eq. 4}) \}^2}{n - p} \right]^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where, n and p are number of results and number of parameters respectively. The ternary excess volumes computed from binary data differ considerably from the measured ternary excess volumes. This shows that the binary mixtures in ternary systems do not behave as they behave in the individual binary systems. Experimental V_{123}^E of the two mixtures are positive (n-butyl acetate + benzene + n-butanol, n-butyl acetate + toluene + n-butanol) over the whole range of composition. This suggests that structure-breaking events are dominant in these mixtures. Ternary excess volume data for other three mixtures are negative over the entire range of composition studied. This suggests that structural effects like (i) formation of a hydrogen bond of the type $X \cdots H-O$ ($X = Cl, Br, NO_2$) between aromatic hydrocarbon in the alcohol and (ii) changes in free volume, interstitial accommodations and conformation changes in n-butyl acetate and aromatic hydrocarbons in the aggregates of alcohol appear to occur in three mixtures (n-butyl acetate + chlorobenzene + n-butanol, n-butyl acetate + bromobenzene + n-butanol, n-butyl acetate + nitrobenzene + n-butanol). Negative values of V^E indicate the presence of strong specific interactions in the binary mixtures containing aromatics. These negative values of V^E may be attri-

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL EXCESS VOLUMES OF TERNARY MIXTURES OF n-BUTYL ACETATE (1) + AROMATIC HYDROCARBON (2) + BUTANOL (3) AT 303.15 K

Mole-fraction of n-butyl acetate	Mole-fraction of aromatic hydrocarbon	\bar{V}_{123}^E (exptl.) $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	V_{123}^E ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)			ΔV_{123}^E $\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
			Redlich-Kister	Kohler	Tsao-Smith	
n-Butyl acetate + Benzene + n-Butanol						
0.047 9	0.082 4	0.096	0.086	0.085	0.087	0.010
0.099 2	0.213 9	0.206	0.161	0.161	0.169	0.045
0.112 2	0.250 3	0.236	0.173	0.173	0.184	0.063
0.097 5	0.386 3	0.264	0.198	0.199	0.208	0.066
0.095 4	0.492 8	0.276	0.205	0.208	0.215	0.071
0.103 5	0.652 7	0.247	0.186	0.192	0.200	0.061
0.105 8	0.693 6	0.228	0.172	0.179	0.186	0.056
0.081 2	0.781 9	0.181	0.143	0.148	0.151	0.037
0.055 7	0.847 4	0.130	0.113	0.117	0.117	0.017
n-Butyl acetate + Toluene + n-Butanol						
0.068 2	0.059 2	0.022	0.020	0.018	0.018	0.002
0.113 9	0.150 3	0.046	0.036	0.029	0.028	0.010
0.094 8	0.312 3	0.082	0.052	0.048	0.054	0.030
0.122 1	0.493 3	0.133	0.082	0.083	0.101	0.051
0.124 6	0.518 4	0.145	0.083	0.085	0.104	0.062
0.083 1	0.563 0	0.141	0.097	0.099	0.110	0.044
0.120 2	0.662 7	0.121	0.073	0.080	0.099	0.048
0.099 4	0.814 1	0.052	0.027	0.033	0.041	0.025
0.081 4	0.840 9	0.040	0.030	0.033	0.039	0.021
n-Butyl acetate + Chlorobenzene + n-Butanol						
0.077 1	0.040 6	-0.017	-0.006	-0.009	-0.008	-0.011
0.107 0	0.144 1	-0.118	-0.071	-0.079	-0.079	-0.047
0.099 0	0.331 7	-0.210	-0.126	-0.133	-0.121	-0.084
0.097 9	0.452 6	-0.204	-0.121	-0.125	-0.106	-0.083
0.116 0	0.485 1	-0.208	-0.124	-0.124	-0.102	-0.104
0.109 0	0.584 5	-0.202	-0.111	-0.108	-0.082	-0.089
0.121 8	0.640 4	-0.206	-0.117	-0.112	-0.083	-0.089
0.081 6	0.799 2	-0.165	-0.124	-0.077	-0.068	-0.041
0.046 8	0.871 9	-0.103	-0.088	-0.042	-0.040	-0.015
n-Butyl acetate+ Bromobenzene + n-Butanol						
0.057 0	0.057 5	-0.058	-0.047	-0.054	-0.051	-0.011
0.106 8	0.179 8	-0.166	-0.110	-0.120	-0.131	-0.056
0.097 1	0.245 1	-0.202	-0.131	-0.139	-0.147	-0.071
0.103 9	0.470 8	-0.199	-0.107	-0.100	-0.099	-0.092
0.115 6	0.513 7	-0.200	-0.098	-0.089	-0.084	-0.102
0.113 0	0.625 7	-0.163	-0.076	-0.069	-0.061	-0.087
0.113 0	0.662 9	-0.160	-0.079	-0.059	-0.049	-0.081
0.105 8	0.739 2	-0.160	-0.096	-0.051	-0.043	-0.064
0.076 3	0.842 1	-0.107	-0.083	-0.036	-0.036	-0.024

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n-Butyl acetate + Nitrobenzene + n-Butanol

0.042 8	0.082 8	-0.084	-0.069	-0.070	-0.067	-0.015
0.102 7	0.177 5	-0.193	-0.126	-0.133	-0.122	-0.067
0.096 5	0.345 2	-0.288	-0.186	-0.184	-0.163	-0.102
0.107 2	0.461 0	-0.315	-0.0199	-0.192	-0.160	-0.116
0.099 6	0.509 6	-0.304	-0.192	-0.182	-0.151	-0.112
0.107 4	0.611 7	-0.299	-0.194	-0.179	-0.144	-0.105
0.105 4	0.689 7	-0.276	-0.189	-0.174	-0.141	-0.087
0.095 3	0.805 5	-0.226	-0.178	-0.168	-0.146	-0.048
0.048 9	0.871 6	-0.107	-0.088	-0.082	-0.078	-0.019

* $\Delta V_{123}^E = V_{123}^E$ (exptl.) - V_{123}^E (b), where V_{123}^E (b) is the excess volume predicted by the Redlich and Kister relation.

buted to the formation of charge transfer complexes between the π -electrons and carbonyl group of n-butyl acetate. Values of V^E obtained here are found to be in reasonable agreement with the previously published values⁶. While comparing the two sets of results for n-butyl acetate + aromatic hydrocarbons + n-propanol⁷ and n-butyl acetate + aromatic hydrocarbons + n-butanol, the replacement of n-propanol by n-butanol does not change the sign of excess volume. However, the algebraic values of V^E is higher for the mixtures containing n-butanol. The positive V^E for benzene, toluene and negative values for the others are probably due to the difference in relative size of the molecules. Thus the present results indicate that attractive interactions are present in mixtures of halo

and NO_2 substituted benzenes.

The introduction of one CH_3 group in benzene (as in toluene) would increase the electron density and hence toluene would have a high electron-donor capacity than benzene. Therefore it would interact more strongly than benzene. This means that the V^E value for toluene-n-butyl acetate-n-butanol should be less than that for benzene-n-butyl acetate-n-butanol. Excess volumes of five mixtures may be attributed to structure-breaking and structure-making effects. Structure-breaking effects include: (i) depolymerisation of alcohol aggregate by halogenated aromatic hydrocarbon and (ii) loss of dipolar association of the three components upon mixing. While structure-breaking effect contributes to expansion in volume, the structure-making effects lead to contraction in volume. The V^E becomes more negative with decreasing π -electron density. This is a proof because the π -electron density of benzene ring decreases when the electron-donating group (methyl) is replaced by an electron-withdrawing substituent (halogen or NO_2 group). Equations (2) and (4) show the best agreement with the experimental data for the first two systems (n-butylacetate + n-butanol + benzene, toluene) whereas equations (2) and (3) show the best agreement with the experimental for the other three systems (n-butyl acetate + n-butanol + chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and nitrobenzene) respectively, at the higher mole fractions, and equation (4) obeys well at lower mole fractions.

Experimental

n-Butyl acetate⁸ (Fluka), n-butanol⁹ (B.D.H.),

TABLE 3-VALUES OF PARAMETERS A_{ij} , B_{ij} AND C_{ij} OF EQUATION (1) AND THE STANDARD DEVIATION $\sigma(V^E)$ AT 303.15 K

System	A_{ij} cm^3 mol^{-1}	B_{ij} cm^3 mol^{-1}	C_{ij} cm^3 mol^{-1}	$\sigma(V^E)$
n-Butylacetate + Benzene	0.142	-0.198	0.130	0.002
n-Butylacetate + Toluene	-0.547	0.037	0.176	0.003
n-Butylacetate + Chlorobenzene	-1.543	0.466	0.383	0.003
n-Butylacetate + Bromobenzene	-1.413	-0.117	0.454	0.004
n-Butylacetate + Nitrobenzene	-2.850	-0.037	0.627	0.003
n-Butylacetate + n-Butanol	0.630	0.232	0.080	0.002
Benzene + n-Butanol	0.830	0.162	0.305	0.004
Toluene + n-Butanol	0.387	0.646	0.016	0.003
Chlorobenzene + n-Butanol	-0.357	0.794	0.054	0.006
Bromobenzene + n-Butanol	-0.382	0.989	-0.169	0.005
Nitrobenzene + n-Butanol	-0.469	0.774	0.035	0.009

TABLE 4—VALUES OF TERNARY CONSTANTS A, B AND C ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) OF THE EQUATIONS (4) AND THE STANDARD DEVIATION $\sigma(\Delta V^E)$ ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) AT 303.15 K

System	A	B	C	$\sigma(\Delta V^E)$
n-Butyl acetate + Benzene + n-Butanol	3.509	7.771	-5.708	0.002
n-Butyl acetate + Toluene + n-Butanol	2.094	22.546	4.052	0.005
n-Butyl acetate + Chlorobenzene + n-Butanol	-4.319	-7.256	-94.155	0.004
n-Butyl acetate + Bromobenzene + n-Butanol	-4.522	-7.231	21.327	0.003
n-Butyl acetate + Nitrobenzene + + n-Butanol	-5.513	-8.762	37.171	0.003

benzene¹⁰ (B.D.H.), toluene¹¹, chlorobenzene¹² and nitrobenzene¹² (all A.R. grade) were purified by reported methods. Bromobenzene (E. Merck) was dried with calcium chloride and fractionally distilled under reduced pressure. The purity of the chemicals was checked by density and boiling point. The density was measured with a standard bicapillary pycnometer with an accuracy of 5 parts in 10⁵.

Excess volumes for the various ternary mixtures were measured with the dilatometer described earlier⁴. Four dilatometers with different capacities were used to cover the mole fractions range 0.1–0.9. Temperature of the water-bath was controlled (± 0.01 K) by means of a toluene regulator and changes in the level of the liquid in the dilatometer capillary was measured with a cathetometer that could be read to ± 0.001 cm. Further, to ensure complete mixing of the components in the capillary, the dilatometer was placed in a cold-bath, so that there was a minimum amount of liquid in the capillary and then returned to the experimental water-bath. This process was repeated two or three times. V^E values were reproducible to within $\pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The experimental method was previously checked by Sreenivasulu and Naidu¹³, for the test system 1,1,1-trichloroethane + 1-propanol + n-heptane and the results showed a standard deviation of $\pm 0.003 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

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